

Press Release Feb 2023

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project meets in Austria to work on joint research strategies

The second meeting of the General Assembly (GnA) of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project will be held at the University of Applied Sciences St. Pölten, Austria, on the 9th and 10th of March. The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, which started in October 2022, is an initiative that aims to increase the research capacity of the European university alliance E³UDRES² - Engaged European Entrepreneurial University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions - and co-create a specific joint research strategy for the alliance.

During these two GnA days, there will be visits to STPUAS laboratories, general meetings with all the work teams, with overviews of the progress of the work and the tasks of each team, as well as work meetings with each team. The meeting will have the on-site participation of at least one member from each work team of each partner and work packages (WP) Leaders. On the morning of the second day, will take place the second meeting of the Executive Board (ExB) of the project, which will be attended by a representative of each institution.

Among the project's objectives is the co-creation of a common strategy and agenda to accelerate the transformation into a European Research and Innovation Center for Smart and Sustainable Regions, as well as to develop structured support programs aimed at enabling scientific communities to fully embrace Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education, Engaged Science and Engaged Education. The project also works to achieve a level playing field in terms of institutional strategies and policies for Human Resources for Research, tackling larger challenges such as brain mobility, new career assessments and joint recruitment strategies.

Another important goal is the development of a structured and integrated framework to harmoniously link all R&I ecosystems and the knowledge triangle of the E³UDRES² alliance of education, research and innovation. To this end, the project promotes dialogue with peer alliances and Higher Education Institutions (HEI), HEI associations, as well as with policy makers. With an innovative and collaborative approach, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project seeks to transform the region into a center of excellence in Research and Innovation, creating a sustainable and intelligent future for all.

E³UDRES²
**ent.r.e.
novators**
ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

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